

**DESCRIPTION OF HUMAN DESTINY IN THE SHORT STORIES OF T.
QAYIPBERGENOV ("SLEEPLESS NIGHTS", "SECRETS KNOWN TO
YOU ALONE")**

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The story "Sleepless Nights" is also one of the important works of the time. In it, a young girl eagerly waits for her parents, but they are dead. After learning about this, the girl sincerely searches for Kasnazar, the person who gave her a second life. Gulzar finds Kasnazar without going back, no matter how hard she goes. While many characters guide her, some of them want to destroy her. This is the winning side of the plot. I cannot be equally good or equally bad characters in life. The writer creates works based on this reality of life in his stories.

After that, a series of lyrical-psychic stories began to appear in Karakalpak literature. Other writers took T. Qaypbergenov's work as an example when creating stories in this genre. The reason is that all the lyrical-psychic stories created in the history of literature appeared after the work of T. Qaypbergenov. This tradition began to appear in the works of writers Sh. Seytov, S. Saliev, U. Pirzhanov.

In the history of literature, the issue of psychologism in the stories created in the 20th century was not left out of research. Literary critic J. Esenov in his scientific work "Secrets of Skill" focused on the issue of skill in stories in Karakalpak literature and gave valuable opinions. Besides being important for the history of literature, work also served as a basis for our scientific work.

T. Qaypbergenov covered the topic of love during the creation of short stories [6]. This feeling is evident in the story "Black Notebook". It describes the life of a young girl, Aisha, who goes through the sweet pain of love. The fact that the writer created this story when he reached the age of the prophet, was of great importance for the value of the story. As an epigraph to the story, he took it from Pushkin's song "From the wonderful ways of secret love, Other things do not enter my head." [3, p. 69]. The lines briefly and clearly reveal the events that will take place in the story. Story is a daily format and does not give rest to the imagination of the black notebook writer. The plot begins with Embergen in the hospital due to a traffic accident. Aisha wishes her lover a cure and shows that she is ready to give her life where it is needed. One evening, he was given the skill to write a letter of recommendation to his lover, to write the letter with sincerity.

Another short story of T. Qaypbergenov based on deep psychologism is "Secret known to yourself". The writer skillfully describes the character of Perikhan in this story. The fact that a person's past has a tragic effect on his fate today leads to a tragic ending. A similar plot can be found in U.Pirzhanov's story "Suwret" (Painting). A soldier falls in love with his sister (unbeknownst to him, of course), and their true love is skillfully portrayed. And T. Qaypbergenov convincingly shows that his first husband, whom he ran away with in his youth, is now in love with Perikhan's daughter Svetlana. It is reliably stated that such a sad situation led to Perikhan's death.

Who caused the death of Perikhan during the reading of the story? - the question arises. Firstly, the early death of his mother, secondly, Nurjan's cruel treatment of his daughter, and thirdly, Jumabay's capriciousness.

True, Svetlana is not the daughter of Paluan, she is the daughter of Jumabai. But these events are not normal for both Perihan and Paluan. The reason was that there were feelings of youthful love between them. The writer leaves it up to the readers to draw conclusions at the end of the story. Paluan and Perikhan's wedding dinner turns into black sadness, Perikhan does not take the secret with him and leaves it to Paluan, whether they will get married or not will remain a mystery.

Literary critic J. Esenov about the story: "In the story, all the events and the thoughts and dreams of the hero take place before our eyes through the reminiscences and inner monologues of Perikhan, who came to his daughter's wedding, in one night." This is one of the most improved principles of psychologism in our national prose" [1, p. 60] - he gives a positive opinion. In short, T. Qaypbergenov was able to make a significant contribution to the development of the story genre in Karakalpak literature with his richly meaningful and skillfully painted story in prose. It is our opinion that the new form, new ideas in his stories have become a real object of research for literary critics. The writer reflected the lifestyle of the Karakalpak people in the 20th century through his artistic work, which is one of the important issues of the time. T. Qaypbergenov occupies a leading place in the evolution of the Karakalpak story.

References:

1. Esenov J. Sheberliktiń sırları. Nókis, Qaraqalpaqstan, 1986. – 96 b.
2. Qayıpbergenov T. Povestler. Nókis: Bilim, 2018. – 244 b.
3. Qayıpbergenov T. Tánhá ózińe málim sır: (Povestler hám publicistikalıq maqalalar). Nókis, Qaraqalpaqstan, 1992. – 407 b.